

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by alkaline periodate

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Manuscript received 25 February 2002, revised 1 October 2002, accepted 24 July 2003

The oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde (2-HNA) by alkaline species of periodate, $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$ has a 1 : 1 stoichiometry and exhibits unit order in $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ and less than unit order each in [2-HNA] and $[\text{OH}^-]$. The reaction proceeds via the formation of an oxidant-substrate complex and its subsequent decomposition in a rate determining step to yield products. The effects of ionic strength, dielectric constant and initially added products have been studied. The reaction constants involved in the mechanism have been computed. There is a good agreement between the observed and calculated rate constants under different experimental conditions of the reaction. The activation parameters have been calculated with respect to the slow step of the proposed mechanism of reaction.

2-Hydroxynaphthaldehyde (2-HNA) is a source of many organic compounds and it is also used in the chromatographic determination of some amino acids. It has got applications in synthetic and pharmaceutical chemistry¹. Although a variety of organic² and inorganic³ substrates are oxidised by periodate, the literature survey reveals that there are no reports on kinetic and mechanistic studies of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by any oxidant. Thus in order to explore the mechanism of oxidation by periodate ion in strongly alkaline medium and to check the selectivity of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde towards periodate, the title reaction was undertaken.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Different sets of reaction mixtures containing different amounts of reactants at constant alkalinity and ionic strength were allowed to react for about 24 h in a closed container, where $[\text{IO}_4^-] > [2\text{-HNA}]$. The remaining IO_4^- was assayed iodometrically⁴. The results showed a ratio of consumption of oxidant to reductant of 1 : 1 as given in eqn. (1),

The main oxidation products identified were 2-hydroxynaphthalic acid by spot test⁵ and iodate by iodometrically. Further the existence of 2-hydroxynaphthalic acid was confirmed by its IR bands at 1647 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 2852 (OH) and 3444 cm^{-1} (OH due to hydrogen bonding).

Reaction order : The kinetic runs of oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by periodate in aqueous alkaline medium were followed at different initial concentration of oxidant, substrate and alkali in turn keeping all other concentrations constant. The reaction orders were determined from the slopes of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs \log concentration plots.

The oxidant, [periodate] was varied in the range of 2.0×10^{-4} to $2.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and the linearity of plots of $\log [\text{IO}_4^-]$ vs time indicates the order in $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ as unity. This was also confirmed by varying $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ which did not show any change in pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} (Table 1). The substrate, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde was varied in the concentration range of 5.0×10^{-3} to $5.0 \times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 27° keeping all other [reactants] constant. The order in [2-HNA] was found to be less than unity (Table 1).

The effect of alkali on the reaction was studied at constant [2-HNA] and $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ keeping constant ionic strength of 0.60 mol dm^{-3} at 27° . The rate constant increased with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 1). The order with respect to alkali was found to be less than unity.

The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the concentration of NaClO_4 from 0.6 to 2.0 mol dm^{-3} other conditions being constant. The rate of reaction remains almost unchanged while increasing the $[\text{NaClO}_4]$. The effect of dielectric constant (D) of the reaction medium on the rate was studied by varying the *t*-butanol-water (Baker sample) content in the reaction mixture. Earlier the inertness of the *t*-butanol towards the oxidant in the reaction mixture had been confirmed. With the increase of *t*-butanol content from 0 to 20% (v/v), the rate remained almost unchanged. The

Table 1. Effect of $[\text{IO}_4^-]$, [2-HNA] and $[\text{OH}^-]$ on oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by alkaline periodate

Temp. = 27° and $I = 0.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{IO}_4^-] \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	[2-HNA] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	$[\text{OH}^-]$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4, \text{ s}^{-1}$	
			Expt.	Calcd.
0.2	1.0	0.1	1.16	1.17
0.4	1.0	0.1	1.12	1.17
1.0	1.0	0.1	1.16	1.17
1.5	1.0	0.1	1.11	1.17
2.0	1.0	0.1	1.15	1.17
1.0	0.5	0.1	0.83	0.82
1.0	1.0	0.1	1.17	1.16
1.0	2.0	0.1	1.45	1.47
1.0	3.0	0.1	1.61	1.61
1.0	5.0	0.1	1.75	1.74
1.0	0.1	0.06	0.89	9.10
1.0	0.1	0.10	1.17	1.16
1.0	0.1	0.20	1.46	1.46
1.0	0.1	0.40	1.66	1.67
1.0	0.1	0.50	1.77	1.76

initially added products such as iodate and 2-hydroxynaphthyllic acid did not show any significant effect on the rate of the reaction. The reaction mixture to which a known amount of acrylonitrile scavenger had been added initially, was kept for 24 h in an inert atmosphere. On dilution of the reaction mixture with methanol, no precipitation occurred, indicating the absence of free radical intervention in the reaction.

Effect of temperature : The rate of reaction was measured at different temperatures under varying [2-HNA]. The rate constants, k of the slow step of Scheme 1 were obtained from the intercept of plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ and these rate constants were used to calculate the activation parameters (Table 2).

Scheme 1

The activity of the periodate as an oxidising agent varies greatly as a function of pH and is capable of subtle con-

Table 2. Activation parameters for the oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde by periodate in aqueous alkaline medium

$[\text{IO}_4^-] = 1 \times 10^{-3}$, [2-HNA] = 1×10^2 , $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1$, $I = 0.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

(a) Effect of temperature :

Temp., °C	$k \times 10^4, \text{ s}^{-1}$
27	1.29
32	1.76
37	2.18
42	3.34

(b) Activation parameters with respect to slow step of Scheme 1 :

E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	48 ± 2
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	46 ± 2
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-166 ± 8
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	97 ± 5

trol. In an aqueous alkaline medium and in the pH range employed, periodate cannot exist as H_4IO_6^- , because in aqueous solution periodate is involved in the following equilibria depending on the pH of the solution,

The species H_4IO_6^- exists near pH 7.0. Hence, under the alkaline conditions employed in the present system, the main species would be expected to be trihydrogen paraperiodate, $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ and dihydrogen paraperiodate, $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$. At higher concentrations, periodate can also undergo dimerisation. The observed fractional order in alkali concentration may be understood in terms of $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$ as the main species in alkaline medium with the following equilibrium, which is also supported by earlier work⁶.

The reaction between periodate and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde in alkaline medium has a stoichiometry 1 : 1 with a first order dependence on the $[\text{IO}_4^-]$, and less than unit order dependence on both the [alkali] and the [substrate]. No effect of added products was observed. The data indicates that the 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde reacts with the active species of periodate to form a complex. The complex formed decomposes in a rate determining step to yield products. The fractional order in substrate concentration, and the non zero intercept of the plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ supports the reaction to occur through a complex formation between the alkaline species of periodate and 2-

hydroxynaphthaldehyde. Furthermore, spectral evidence for such a complex was obtained from the UV-visible spectra of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde and mixture of periodate and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde. A bathochromic shift (λ_{\max}) of 7 nm from 360–367 is observed. Such type of oxidant-substrate complexes have been reported in earlier studies⁷. Taking all the experimental results into consideration, a mechanism as in Scheme 1 may be proposed.

The probable structure of the complex (C) is

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (6)

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{IO}_4^-]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}][\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (6)$$

The rate equation (6) may be rearranged to equation (7) which is suitable for verification.

$$\frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[2\text{-HNA}][\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[2\text{-HNA}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

From equation (7), it is evident that the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ are expected to be linear ($r = 0.9985$, $s = 0.032$) and are found to be so (Fig. 1). From the slopes and intercepts of such plots, the values of K_1 , K_2 and k were evaluated as 0.3 ± 0.01 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), $5.1 \pm 0.2 \times 10^3$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and $2.0 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-4}$ (s^{-1}) respectively. By using the values of K_1 , K_2 and k , the rate constants under different experimental conditions were calculated and which are in good agreement with the experimental rate constants (Table 1).

The negligibly small effects of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the reaction rates are presumably due to the fact that the reaction occurs in between a neutral and a charged species which is evident⁸ from the mechanism (Scheme 1). The negative value of entropy of activation is in agreement with the formation of activated complex in-

Fig. 1. Verification of rate law (6) in the form of (7). Plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[2\text{-HNA}]$ and plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ (conditions as in Table 1).

involved in the reaction. Observed modest enthalpy activation, a relatively low value of the entropy of activation indicate that the oxidation presumably occurs by an inner-sphere mechanism. This conclusion is supported by earlier work⁹.

It is interesting to note that, periodate (existing as periodic acid in acid medium) being one of the strongest oxidising agents in acidic medium, the oxidation of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde in acid medium does not take place even in presence of different catalysts. But in alkaline medium, the reaction takes place with measurable velocity, thus receiving the attention to study the activity of periodate in such media.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Stock solution of periodate was prepared by dissolving potassium metaperiodate (Riedel) and used after keeping for 24 h; its concentration was verified iodometrically⁴. 2-Hydroxynaphthaldehyde solution was prepared in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution. Sodium perchlorate was used to maintain a constant ionic strength and NaOH to get the required alkalinity. Potassium iodate solution was prepared in distilled water.

A regression analysis of experimental data, in order to obtain the regression coefficient (r), and the standard deviation (s), of points from the regression line, was performed with a computer PENTIUM I processor.

Kinetic runs : All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions at $27 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless stated

otherwise. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostated solutions of periodate and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde which also contained the necessary quantities of NaOH and NaClO₄ to maintain the required alkalinity and ionic strength respectively. Here the total concentration of hydroxyl ion was calculated considering sodium hydroxide in 2-HNA as well as the sodium hydroxide additionally added. The course of reaction was followed by determining the concentration of unreacted periodate in aliquots (5 ml each) of the reaction mixture by titrating against standard sodium thiosulfate at neutral pH maintained by dihydrogen phosphate⁴. Such titrations were carried out at regular intervals.

The reaction was generally followed over a period longer than three half-lives. The first order rate constants were obtained from the slopes of log [IO₄⁻] vs time plots. The rate constants were reproducible to within ±5%. The effect of dissolved oxygen on the rate of the reaction was checked by preparing the reaction mixture and following the reaction in a nitrogen atmosphere. No significant difference between the results obtained under N₂ atmosphere and in presence of air was observed.

In view of the ubiquitous contamination of carbonate in basic solutions, the effect of carbonate on the reaction was studied. Added carbonate showed no effect on the reaction rate. However, fresh solutions were used while conducting the experiments.

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